

Evaluating the visual communication component of a nutrition education intervention: a question of visual representational latitude

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Abstract

The paper discusses an *ex post* evaluation of the visual communication component of a nutrition education intervention in an elderly target group at a care centre in Sharpeville, South Africa. Pauwels' concept of visual representational latitude (VRL) was taken as a point of departure to measure the comprehensibility of thirteen different semantic units that formed part of nutrition education pamphlets and posters. The results indicate that the average respondent in the sample of 140 participants was only able to recognise 49% of the subject matter depicted, and comprehended 29.1% of the pictorial conventions employed. The paper illustrates how the concept of VRL was operationalised in practice and highlights that a crucial first step in the evaluation of visual illustrations is to establish to what extent the basic 'building blocks' of the visual communication process, i.e. object recognition and comprehension of pictorial conventions, are in place.

Introduction

This paper reports on an evaluation of the visual communication component of a nutrition education intervention conducted at a care centre for the elderly¹ in Sharpeville, South Africa. The centre is located in the Vaal region of the Gauteng province, parts of which are characterised by high levels of unemployment, (verbal) illiteracy (see Slabbert, 2004) and low Living Standards Measure (LSM) scores as benchmarked by the South African Advertising Research Foundation (SAARF, 2006). The nutrition education programme at the care centre for the elderly is based on the nationally standardised Food Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDG's) of South Africa and aims – within the context of sustainable community development - to promote improved food procurement as well as food consumption patterns, and to contribute towards addressing

¹ As part of an agreement with the community in which the study was conducted, the researchers undertook not to disclose the name of the centre in scholarly publications in order to further protect the anonymity of the study participants.

malnutrition and household food insecurity in affected communities. As 58.2% of the community members who regularly attend activities at the care centre for the elderly reported that they have received seven or less years of formal schooling (18.8% indicated having received no formal schooling at all), one of the components of the nutrition education programme involves communicating nutrition education messages visually, i.e. by means of visual illustrations, where the reliance on the accompanying verbal code or 'text anchor' is minimal. The comprehensibility and overall suitability of the pamphlets and posters currently in use for the purpose of nutrition education was, however, not known. In the light thereof, the visual illustrations were evaluated.

Concepts from the visual communication literature

According to a recent rhizome analysis of visual communication by Moriarty and Barbatsis (2005:xiii), in visual communication - and, by implication, in a sub-field of visual communication such as development communication design - 'there is no unifying theory, nor should there be, because the area represents the intersection of thought from many diverse traditions'. The underlying logic of a rhizome analysis is that, in contrast to the metaphor of a tree (of knowledge) where the trunk represents a core theory from which offshoots or branches - i.e. sub-disciplines - emerge, the metaphor of a rhizome (with roots and offshoots, but no trunk) is better suited to a transdisciplinary field of inquiry such as visual communication. In other words, a rhizome analysis aims to map out the 'non-hierarchical systems of deterritorialized lines that connect with other lines in random, unregulated relationships' (Best and Kellner 1991:98). In the rhizome analysis of visual communication conducted by Moriarty and Barbatsis (2005), visual literacy is labelled as an 'intersection' item, in contrast to other components of the rhizomatic map labelled as 'molar' (art, history and sociology, for example) or 'molecular' (critical studies, semiotics and law, for instance). Visual literacy is thus classed - together with visual culture, graphic design and photography, among many others - as a component of visual communication studies that is characterised by an 'intersection of thought' (Moriarty and Barbatsis, 2005:xiii) from a wide variety of theoretical perspectives and traditions of theorising.

In the absence of a core or 'mother' theory of visual communication, especially in a development communication context, the present evaluation was primarily guided by Pauwels' concept of visual representational latitude (VRL). VRL is one of several elements in an integrated theoretical framework of visual representational literacy as applied to scientific discourse, where the target audience does not necessarily consist exclusively of scientists, but may also comprise members of the general public, students and/or other stakeholders. According to Pauwels (2005:6), VRL refers to 'coping with controlled and uncontrolled variations in the

depicted and the depiction'. In other words, VRL relates to (a) an inability or difficulty to express visually the degree of variation of the depicted referent (i.e. variation of the depicted), and (b) an uncertainty as to the necessity or degree of motivation, as well as the meaning or status, of the chosen forms and visual elements (i.e. variation of the depiction) (Pauwels, 2005:6). The concept of VRL primarily plays itself out on two dimensions. Firstly, on the production dimension, VRL is determined - among others - by the strengths and limitations inherent to the medium used to convey variations in the phenomenon or process depicted, as well as the manner in which the medium is utilised, i.e. the 'room to maneuver' (Pauwels, 2005:6) that the given medium allows. One of the examples which Pauwels uses to illustrate the challenge of depicting variations of the referent visually is that it is reasonably uncomplicated to explain verbally that a certain bird species has three to seven spots (presumably of identical size) on each of its wings. A visual representation of that particular bird species would, however, typically not convey that the number of spots varies within the range of three to seven. Five different birds may be drawn, for instance, each with a different number of spots per wing, in the hope, firstly, that the viewer notices that the number of spots varies between birds, and, secondly, that the viewer correctly concludes on seeing the images of five different birds that only three to seven spots are possible, i.e. that a bird of the given species with two and less, or eight and more spots, does not exist. That is not to say that the concept of VRL engages with the limits of depiction *per se*, such as Worth's well-known argument that 'pictures can't say ain't' (Worth, 1981:184), i.e. that images do not have the formal capability of depicting negative events, and that it consequently makes more sense to formulate the meaning of an image along an exist-did not exist continuum as opposed to a true-false continuum, for example. Rather, on the production dimension, VRL refers to how variation in the phenomenon or process was conveyed visually, i.e. whether appropriate levels of iconicity and abstraction were chosen, as well as the manner in which the given medium – or combination of media - was used to achieve this (Pauwels, 2005:6).

Secondly, on the reception dimension, VRL is mainly determined by the extent to which the target audience - or aggregate of individual viewers - considers what is depicted to be 'necessarily so' on the one hand or 'just one way of putting it' on the other hand (Pauwels, 2005:6). In other words, a visual text with a wide VRL leaves the viewer uncertain – or even confused - about the meaning and status of the visual elements of which it is comprised, and how these visual elements relate to actual variance in the phenomena and/or processes depicted. In contrast, a visual text with a narrow VRL conveys the extent and nature of variance in the referent in such a manner that the members of the target group consider the choice of forms and visual elements contained therein as motivated, i.e. as selected with a view to convey variance

visually within the capabilities of the chosen medium of dissemination. Pauwels refers to the example of an illustration of a phenomenon from physics, where a core is depicted with twenty three identical particles revolving around this core, presumably in a random fashion. Such an image may give rise to uncertainty in the target group whether the number of particles is always fixed, or whether the illustration aims to convey nothing more than that a large number of particles revolve around the core. This type of uncertainty is typically dispelled by means of an accompanying verbal code, such as an extended legend or written narrative (or oral clarification in the case of an illiterate target group), that defines the ‘representational claims’ (Pauwels, 2005:7) made. The comprehension of the various representational claims a visual text may contain may be assessed on three distinct semiotic levels, i.e. the syntactic, semantic and pragmatic levels of comprehension. These terms derive from a theoretical framework by Goldsmith (1984), based on terminology used in earlier work by Morris (1938). According to Goldsmith’s framework, syntactic comprehension involves the ability to perceive depth, figure-ground relationships and colour, but does not include the recognition of objects. It thus refers to a basic perceptual competence on the part of the viewer, as opposed to an interpretational competence, i.e. to recognise and attach significance to the image contents, which is measured on the semantic and pragmatic levels. As successfully conveying variance in the referent primarily depends on the interpretational competence of the viewer, and not on the perceptual competence (even though perceptual competence may be regarded as a pre-requisite for semantic and pragmatic comprehension), the concept of VRL mainly applies to the semantic and pragmatic levels of comprehension. The semantic level of comprehension concerns the ability to recognise depicted objects, and to identify what they denote, in contrast to pragmatic comprehension, which may be defined as the ability to interpret a visual message beyond its literal meaning, implying an ability to comprehend figurative meanings and a familiarity with artistic manipulation and/or cultural conventions (Goldsmith, 1984:124).

Aims of the evaluation

While the terms ‘readability’ and ‘appropriateness’ are at times used interchangeably in the context of a visual message, readability in a general sense concerns the ease with which the preferred meaning of a visual text is understood in a particular target group (Pettersson, 1993:159), whereas appropriateness usually refers to a concept broader than readability that may be defined as the overall effectiveness with which the communicative objective of a visual text is achieved in a specified setting (Hugo, 1997:8). As Davies (1984:24) puts it, appropriateness

implies that ‘in order to make an efficient an effective contribution, media, like a key, must be shaped, cut, chipped, designed so that it exactly fits the situation’.

The present evaluation focused on the readability of the nutrition education visuals rather than their appropriateness and dealt primarily with the basic 'building blocks' – i.e. with the semantic level - of the visual communication process, as opposed to the extent to which the target group understood nuanced and figurative meanings of the nutrition education pamphlets and posters advocating correct serving sizes. Specific aims of the evaluation were to measure (a) the VRL on the level object recognition, or whether a sample of the target group were able to identify correctly (a sample of) the referents depicted, (b) the appropriateness of the visual-verbal balance of the illustrations, i.e. whether the respondents preferred more images or more written text in the pamphlets and posters, and (c) the VRL of a sample of pictorial conventions (speech bubbles, arrows etc.) as used in the pamphlets and posters.

Method

The *ex post* evaluation of the readability of the nutrition education visuals currently used at the care centre for the elderly involved a ten to fifteen minute session conducted in the home language of the respondent during which a field worker completed a questionnaire about the visual communication component of the nutrition education materials in the presence of the respondent. By limiting the duration of the session, fatigue-related data collection issues were minimised. Sampling occurred in two phases. Firstly, a sample of ten semantic units was randomly chosen for the purpose of measuring object recognition and three semantic units were randomly selected in order to assess the comprehension of pictorial conventions. This sample of thirteen semantic units represented approximately ten percent of the total number of visual semantic units in the pamphlets and posters (see Figure 1 for an example of these). For instance, an image of a plate with a butternut, a drumstick and porridge on it (bottom left image in Figure 1) was seen as consisting of several separate semantic units, i.e. the image as a whole was one semantic unit, the image of the butternut was one semantic unit, the image of the porridge was one semantic unit and so on.

Secondly, the total number of elderly (mean age 71.7 years), primarily Sesotho-speaking (84.7%) and pre-dominantly female (87.1%) community members who regularly attend activities at the care centre for the elderly, and for whom accurate data regarding their nutritional status has been collected, is 170. Of these, a sample of 140 community members (i.e. 82.3%) voluntarily participated in the evaluation of the visual material on a first come first serve and anonymous basis (anonymous in the sense that their name or other personal particulars were not recorded on

the questionnaire). In the first part of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to identify the objects depicted in the ten randomly chosen semantic units. Depending on the answer received, a score of one point (correct or envisaged answer), half a point (borderline answer) or zero points (incorrect answer) was allocated and the ten responses were used to calculate an object recognition score on a scale ranging from zero to ten points. For instance, an image of an orange was pointed out to the respondent by the field worker (see the top right of Figure 1, but note that a mask with a rectangular window was placed over the pamphlet shown in Figure 1) and the respondent was requested to identify the object depicted. The respondents were also asked to declare on a three-point scale whether the size of the images made object recognition difficult, in line with the recommendations by Nitzke et al. (1986) and Townsend & Kaiser (2005:176), among others, that a limited number of response options should be used for low-literacy audiences. Where object recognition was impeded due to an inappropriate image size, a score of one point was allocated. In cases where a different image size would have made object recognition only slightly or partially easier, a score of two points was awarded, and in instances where the respondent replied that the size of an image made no difference to object recognition at all, this was indicated with a score of three points.

In the second part of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to describe the meaning of the pictorial conventions used in three different semantic units. The answers were recorded as a score of one point (correct or envisaged answer), half a point (borderline answer) or zero points (incorrect answer). From the responses to these three questions, a comprehension of pictorial convention score was calculated on a scale ranging from zero to three points. For example, the respondents were presented with an illustration of a box of matches depicted next to an image of a slice of cheese of exactly the same image size. The respondents were asked what meanings they attach to the illustration in order to measure to what extent their answers conform to the envisaged meaning that one serving of cheese should correspond to the size of a box of matches. Further, the respondent was asked to indicate whether the visual-verbal balance in the educational material is appropriate. The answers were recorded in three categories, i.e. (a) more images would have been better, to which a score of 1 was assigned, (b) the balance between images and writing is just right (associated with a score of 2), or (c) more writing would have been better (associated with a score of 3). Each session was preceded by a brief orientation about the nature of the project as well as ethical issues (voluntary participation, anonymity, handling of responses etc.). Each session ended with the field worker giving the respondent the opportunity to explain how the nutrition education pamphlets and posters used at the care centre for the elderly could be improved in general terms and, thereafter, thanking the respondent for

participating. The questionnaire was piloted in an initial group of thirty respondents to check that the session duration fell within the envisaged ten to fifteen minutes and to ensure that all the questions were clearly formulated. Only minor adjustments to the questionnaire were needed before the main data collection process commenced.

Result

The mean age of the respondents in the sample (n = 140) was 70.7 years, with 84.3% indicating that their home language is Sesotho. The remaining 15.7% reported Setswana (4.3%), Xhosa (5.7%) and Zulu (5.7%) as the home language. The respondents in the sample were primarily female (85%). As Table 1 shows, the results indicate - in short - that the average respondent in the sample of 140 participants was only able to recognise 49% of the subject matter depicted (a mean object recognition score of 4.90 on a scale of zero to ten, i.e. 49%). Further, the average respondent correctly comprehended less than a third of the pictorial conventions used (a mean score of 0.97 on a scale of zero to three, i.e. 29.1%).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of questionnaire responses

Questionnaire item	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Var.
Object recognition score, i.e. the sum of ten separate responses; the minimum final score possible is zero, the maximum final score possible is ten.	140	0	10	4.90	2.177	4.741
Role of image size, i.e. did the size of the images make object recognition difficult? The minimum score possible is one, the maximum score possible is three.	140	1	3	1.81	0.755	0.570
Comprehension of pictorial convention score, i.e. the sum of three separate responses; the minimum final score possible is zero, the maximum final score possible is three.	140	1	3	0.97	1.006	1.012
Visual-verbal balance, i.e. is the visual-verbal balance in the illustrations appropriate? The minimum score possible is one, the maximum score possible is three.	139	1	3	1.65	0.574	0.329

Key: N = number of responses; Min = minimum score in cases analysed; Max. = maximum score in cases analysed; SD = standard deviation; Var. = variance.

The object recognition scores, which represent the sum of ten separate responses, as described earlier, where the minimum final score possible is zero and the maximum final score possible is ten, ranged from zero to ten points in the sample (see Figure 2). This contrasts sharply with the ‘ideal’ range of eight to ten points, i.e. the range visual communicators in the context of nutrition education aim for, where there are no significant impediments or barriers to object recognition the target group. The lowest number of correct or envisaged responses was recorded for a clip art image, similar in style to the visual elements in Figure 1, which depicted a tennis ball. This semantic unit was recognised by 29

of the 140 respondents, i.e. by 20.7%. The highest number of correct or envisaged responses was received for a semantic unit depicting a partially peeled banana (top left in Figure 1), which 132 of the 140 respondents, or 94.3%, identified correctly. Where a study participant supplied an answer along the lines of ‘fruit’ rather than ‘banana’, or more specifically ‘peeled banana’, this was recorded as a borderline response (scoring half a point as discussed earlier). Stated differently, a narrow VRL was assumed during data collection, in the sense that when a respondent was shown a particular semantic unit and asked by the field worker to identify what is depicted - i.e. what the referent is - the correct or envisaged answer was a ‘necessarily so’ type of answer (peeled banana), rather than a ‘just one way of putting it’ type of answer (fruit) (Pauwels, 2005:6).

According to the data the questionnaire yielded, the size of the images was seen by the respondents as only a minor factor impacting on object recognition. On a scale of one to three points, the mean score in the sample was 1.81. In other words, the majority of study participants reported that a different image size would have made object recognition only slightly or partially easier. That is not to say that the respondents found the image size acceptable in general terms. When invited at the end of the session to make general comments or observations about how the nutrition education pamphlets and posters used at the care centre for the elderly could be improved, an answer along the lines of ‘the images should be bigger’ was the most frequently recorded reply, possibly due to poor eyesight typically encountered in an elderly target group.

As far as the comprehension of pictorial conventions is concerned, Table 1 shows that the comprehension of pictorial conventions score, which represents the sum of three separate responses, where the minimum final score possible is zero and the maximum final score possible is three, ranged from one point to three points in the sample of respondents, with a mean score of 0.97. The comprehension of pictorial conventions was lowest in a semantic unit which aimed to convey visually that the correct serving size for dry pasta is equivalent to the amount of dry pasta that fits into a cupped hand. Of the 140 respondents, 31 respondents, or 22.1%, correctly indicated the preferred or envisaged meaning of the illustration. The comprehension of pictorial conventions was highest in the case of a semantic unit illustrating that the correct serving size for a portion of red meat, chicken or fish is equivalent to the size of a pack of playing cards, where 62 of the 140 respondents (44.3%) supplied the correct or envisaged answer. In other words, the VRL as measured in the context of basic pictorial conventions (in this case primarily involving the associational juxtapositioning of visual elements, see Messaris, 1994: 37) was found to be wide. Specifically, the data collected

suggests that the average respondent was confused and uncertain about the representational claims made on the semantic level of signification in the visual material.

Lastly, the majority of respondents indicated that the visual-verbal balance of the nutrition education illustrations used during data collection was on the whole appropriate (a mean score of 1.65 on a scale of one to three points). This score was, however, partially contradicted by the general comments recorded at the end of the session during which some of the respondents stated that there should be ‘more images’ in the nutrition education material used at their centre. Taken together, it is probably safe to conclude that the visual-verbal balance of the material was not regarded as a burning issue in the sample of respondents, but in the event that changes or improvements are made to the existing materials, these should preferably involve a shift towards more images. In this regard, it is interesting to note that the nutrition education materials evaluated in this study, of which Figure 1 is an example, are mainly Type IV or Type V texts according to Wileman’s (1993) verbo-visual continuum. In a Type IV text, the visual and verbal components are balanced, i.e. carry equal semantic weight, in contrast to a Type V text, which consists of a visual image with accompanying verbal cues that closely relate to the meaning of what is depicted, such as a line drawing of a flower with written labels. The result of the present study thus confirms the rule of thumb that Type V to Type VII (images only) texts, rather than Type IV texts, should be used in low-literate target groups.

Conclusion

The evaluation reported on in this paper has several implications for theory and practice. Firstly, from a nutrition education perspective, the larger question in the Vaal region, where the care centre for the elderly is located, is to what extent nutrition education programmes, as interventions, ultimately influence, among others, (voluntary) changes in dietary intake, food procurement patterns and household food insecurity across diverse target groups and communities. While it is generally accepted that visual illustrations and the various representational claims they may contain play only a minor role in the overall programme to address malnutrition through health education and development, they are, nonetheless, important cog wheels in the bigger machinery. In this regard, the outcome of the present evaluation highlights that the comprehensibility and/or readability of visual illustrations utilised for the purposes of nutrition education cannot be taken for granted – even on a very rudimentary level – and, accordingly, the need to assess and monitor their communicative value as thoroughly as possible cannot be over-emphasised.

Secondly, from a visual communication theory perspective, the paper illustrates how the (abstract) concept of VRL was operationalised in practice, specifically with regard to object recognition and basic pictorial conventions on the semantic level of comprehension. As noted by (Pauwels, 2005:6), VRL is:

‘not just a producer’s (or sender’s) problem; that is, it is not just a matter of deciding how to express variation, of choosing the right level of iconicity or abstraction for a specific purpose. It is also a user’s (or receiver’s) problem: what kinds of variation is to be expected in the real world, and which elements in this particular representation are ‘motivated’ by a perceived reality, and which others are due to specific, intentional, or unintentional choices of the producer, limitations of the medium or larger production context?’

It is precisely because VRL, as a theoretical construct, accommodates both the producer(s) having to cope with variation in the referent, as well as the member(s) of the target group having to cope with uncertainties regarding the depiction of variance –i.e. the semantic instability of the visual language used - that it proved so useful as a theoretical basis for the evaluation reported on in this paper, which was undertaken with a view to understand how the nutrition education material currently in use at the care centre for the elderly could be improved if necessary. That is not to say that the paper covered all of the ramifications of the VRL concept. However, the evaluation outcome clearly indicates that measuring the VRL on the ‘building blocks’ level of visual communication, involving object recognition and basic pictorial conventions rather than figurative meanings, elaborate connotations and/or personal associations, is an indispensable first step when applying the VRL concept in practice, especially in the context of a low-literate target group.

Thirdly, from a methodological perspective, the evaluation considered in this paper raises some interesting issues surrounding the notion of causality. It is tempting to conclude, based on the empirical data collected in this study, that adjusting or correcting the wide VRL in the illustrations evaluated is likely to ‘cause’ their comprehensibility to rise, or will lead to them being better understood in the sample of respondents (or in a comparable target group for that matter). While this is almost certainly the case, it raises the question on what basis a causal relationship may in fact be assumed. As Mouton (1994:86) points out, according to the deductive-nomological model of explanation (i.e. the nomothetic model), demonstrating causation requires a regular relationship between events. However, as Mouton (1994:81) shows,

it is a mistake to blindly link causation to regularity and that ‘in contrast to the common wisdom, co-variation between events is *not* a necessary condition for the presence of a causal relationship’. In other words, when causality is interpreted as ‘the operation of the causal powers of entities’ (Mouton, 1994:81) rather than as a regular relationship between events, it follows that issues and concerns relating to the comprehensibility and/or readability of nutrition education visuals and their target group-specific VRL revolve primarily around questions of regularity and not causation *per se*. This is because visual communicators working in the context of nutrition education aim to produce visual illustrations where the referent depicted is correctly recognised, and the envisaged meaning of pictorial conventions employed to convey nutrition education messages visually is accurately understood by the target group on a regular, predictable basis, i.e. each time the illustration is viewed. The challenge for visual communicators working in the field of nutrition education does thus not only lie with producing visual illustrations that have a narrow VRL, are easily comprehended and highly readable in a given target group. The challenge extends to ensuring that this is regularly the case.

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Figure 1. Example of nutrition education pamphlet

What **5 a day** looks like as part of a healthy diet!

Figure 2. Normal curve of object recognition score (N = 140, Mean = 4.90)

